

PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THINKING IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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The theories of thinking existing in modern psychology reflect various approaches to the study of thinking and reveal the essence, structure and features of the flow of mental activity in children of different ages in various processes of activity.

The wide social demand for the study of the development of preschool children in modern dynamically changing conditions increases the relevance of research in the field of psychology.

In the theoretical analysis of the problems of the development of thinking in preschool children, we will focus on a number of points: firstly, on the analysis of research on the means of thinking related to actions and operations and methods of its implementation; secondly, we will consider two main directions of the development of thinking in preschool children - logical and dialectical;

The psychology of thinking in preschool children, on the one hand, is a fairly well-studied area of developmental psychology, on the other hand, there is uncertainty in the interpretation of this complex cognitive process at a given age. It is customary to evaluate thinking in ontogenesis from the point of view of the means and methods of its implementation, since in psychology, thinking itself is considered as an indirect and generalized reflection process. L.S. Vygotsky's work "Thinking and Speech" is devoted to the study of the means of thinking. Several types of interpretation of the development of thinking in the ontogenesis proposed by the scientist are proposed: visually effective, visually figurative, verbal and logical types of the cognitive process are distinguished[1].

The thinking of preschool children and its development have their own characteristics. Thinking begins to develop very rapidly during the preschool period. This is due, firstly, to the relatively increased life experience of preschool children, secondly, to the

well-developed speech of children during this period, and thirdly, to the ability of preschool children to act freely and independently.

The emergence of questions in preschool children in all areas indicates the activation of their thinking. If a child cannot find an answer to his question or if adults do not pay attention to his question, his curiosity begins to fade.

Usually, any thinking process arises from surprise, amazement, and as a result, various questions arise. Many parents and some educators, if children ask too many questions, say, "Don't be too flattering," "Where did you learn such things?" As a result, the child becomes shy and tries to understand as best he can. Some shy children do not ask any questions at all. Adults themselves should ask such children questions during various activities and trips, thus activating them.

Any thinking usually begins with comparing, analyzing, and synthesizing something. Therefore, we call this comparison, analysis, and synthesis the thinking process. Traveling helps to activate and develop the thinking process in children. During trips to nature, children compare, analyze, and synthesize different things. Sensory standards are shown in the works of L.A. Wenger as a tool for thinking in preschool children[2]. A number of authors note that in preschool children, along with visual thinking, verbal-logical thinking also becomes relevant. So, Y.A.L.Kolominsky writes about this: "the transition from visual thinking to verbal-logical thinking occurs in the middle of preschool age"[3].

Thinking cannot exist as a separate mental process, it develops together with all other cognitive processes in perception, attention, imagination, memory, speech. Along with the change in the content of the child's knowledge of the environment, the nature of mental activity, new forms of thinking appear. Children of this age are curious, ask a lot of questions, are interested in everything they see around them: people, animals, natural phenomena. A preschool child reacts differently to the intellectual task facing him, the range of tasks also expands. To solve it, he uses other methods, he generalizes the observed phenomena in a different way.

Thus, considering the development of thinking in a preschool child, it is necessary to take into account two interrelated aspects of this process: a change in its content and the emergence of new forms of intellectual activity of the child. Preschool children receive new knowledge from adults, in games, on walks, during various experiments and in other types of children's activities.

List of used literature

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